

EFFECTS OF FIBRE SURFACE PLASMA TREATMENT ON INTERLAMINAR
SHEAR AND FLEXURAL PROPERTIES OF ARAMID/EPOXY
AND EXTENDED CHAIN POLYETHYLENE/EPOXY COMPOSITES

James R. Brown, Philip J. C. Chappell and Zdenka Mathys
Materials Research Laboratory (MRL)-DSTO,
PO Box 50, Ascot Vale, Victoria 3032 Australia

ABSTRACT

Substantial improvements in the interlaminar shear and flexural strengths of aramid/epoxy and extended chain polyethylene (ECPE)/epoxy composites, as well as in the flexural modulus of ECPE/epoxy composites, are observed when the fibres are pretreated in an ammonia plasma. These property changes are examined in terms of the chemistry of the fibre surface and the microscopic properties of the fibre/matrix interface. Fracture surface micrographs show that after plasma treatment of the fibres the shear failure mode changes from clean interfacial shear fracture to fibre fibrillation and matrix cracking as well as, for ECPE, shear failure within the fibres. This change suggests that plasma treatment strengthens fibre/matrix bonding, in accord with the observed increase in interlaminar shear strength. A comparison with corona treated ECPE suggests that the stronger bonding may be due to specific interactions between surface amine groups and the epoxy resin. Failure of flexural test specimens occurs in compression, and the enhanced flexural strength of composites containing plasma-treated fibres results mainly from reduced compressive fibre buckling and debonding due to stronger interfacial bonding.

KEYWORDS: Fiber, Aramid; Fiber, Polyethylene; Matrix, Epoxy; Strength, Shear; Strength, Flexural; Interface; Failure, Interlaminar.

1. INTRODUCTION

Aramid and extended chain polyethylene (ECPE) fibre-reinforced composites are characterised by a relatively low fibre/matrix interfacial strength and are therefore less than ideal for structural applications. In order to overcome this problem, it is necessary to modify the fibre surface to induce chemical or physical interactions with the resin matrix.

With aramids, the primary aim in improving interfacial bonding has been to maximise filament wettability, with chemical bond formation as a secondary

objective. This has involved both etching (1) and chemical modification (2-5) of the filament surface. The improvements in interlaminar properties achieved by more aggressive treatments (2,3) have been accompanied by substantial losses in filament strength. However, milder chemical treatments (4,5) and ammonia or monomethylamine plasma treatments (6) have resulted in significant improvements in interlaminar properties of aramid composites without accompanying mechanical degradation of the filaments. Despite this success, however, it is still not clear whether the improvements result primarily from physical or chemical interactions. A broad range of surface treatments, generally oxidative in nature, have been used to increase wettability of ECPE fibres and adhesion to the resin matrix. These include chemical oxidation (7,8), corona treatment (9) and oxygen plasma treatment (8-10). The latter has also been shown to cause roughening or micropitting of the fibre surface, and it has been suggested that mechanical interlocking to the matrix resin is also influential in promoting fibre/matrix adhesion (8,9).

This paper considers the chemical aspects of treatment of aramid and ECPE fibres in ammonia plasma, the response of interlaminar and flexural properties of aramid/epoxy and ECPE/epoxy composites to the surface treatment, and the microscopic basis for failure in these composites.

2. EXPERIMENTAL TECHNIQUES

2.1 Aramid and ECPE Fabrics Aramid fabric (Kevlar® 49, style 352, 1150 denier), woven and scoured by Clark-Schwebel Fiber Glass Corporation, was obtained from Du Pont (Australia) Ltd. The fabric was cleaned by Soxhlet extraction in water and then acetone and dried for 24 hours at 105°C before use. Untreated and corona treated ECPE fabrics (Spectra® 1000, 650 denier) were obtained from Allied Signal Corporation and were used without cleaning.

2.2 Plasma Treatment of Fabrics Ammonia plasma treatments were carried out in a 13.56 MHz capacitively coupled plasma reactor using a reactor power of 100 W, a pressure of 0.25 Torr and a gas flow rate of 20 standard cm³/min.

2.3 Surface Characterisation of Plasma-treated Fabrics Plasma treatment in ammonia resulted in the incorporation of amine groups onto the fibre surfaces. The amine concentration was measured by dye assay, using the azo-sulfonate dye Crocein Orange G (CI 15970, Sigma Chemicals C-3268) and the technique described by Allred (6). Briefly, amine groups on the fibre surface were protonated by acid treatment, and the counter anion was exchanged for the dye anion. The bound dye was then eluted with a base and its concentration was determined spectrophotometrically using the absorption maximum at 480 nm.

The number of surface amine groups per nm², N, is given by:

$$N = \frac{6.023C}{MWA} \quad (1)$$

where M is the molecular weight of the dye, W is the weight of the fabric

sample (g), C is the dye concentration (ppm) in a 10 cm³ sample and A is the specific surface area of the fibre (aramid: 0.233 m²/g, ECPE: 0.137 m²/g).

2.4 Composite Fabrication Composites were fabricated from both untreated and plasma-treated fabrics and the diglycidyl ether of bisphenol A (DGEBA) (Shell Epon 828) and diamino-diphenyl methane (DDM). Fibre treatment times are given in Table 1. The fabrics were impregnated by passing samples through a solution containing 120g DGEBA, 32.4g DDM and 234g methyl ethyl ketone. The solvent was evaporated at room temperature for 30 min and then at 80°C for a further 15 min. The impregnated fabric composites were cured for 2 h at 80°C and 2 h at 120°C at a pressure of 350 kPa. The matrix content was nominally 34%. Individual values are listed in Tables 1 and 2.

2.5 Interlaminar Shear Strength (ILSS) The ILSS of the aramid/epoxy composites was determined using the four-point shear test method of Browning et al. (11). Specimen dimensions were nominally 50 x 10 x 4 mm (20 plies), with a span length/depth ratio, L/d, of 11.5. The ILSS of the ECPE/epoxy composites was measured using the short-beam shear method (12). Specimen dimensions were nominally 60 x 10 x 10 mm (30 plies), with L/d of 4. Specimens were conditioned at 23°C and 50% RH for 24 h before testing in an Instron testing machine at crosshead speeds of 2 mm/min (aramid) and 1 mm/min (ECPE).

The interlaminar shear strength, T, for both methods is given by:

$$T = \frac{3P}{4bd} \quad (2)$$

where P is the failure load, b is the beam width and d is the beam depth.

2.6 Flexural Properties The flexural properties of the composites were determined in accordance with standard flexure test procedures (13) using a three point loading system for aramid/epoxy composites, and a four point loading system with a load span equal to one-third of the support span for ECPE/epoxy composites.

Aramid modulus specimens with nominal dimensions 300 x 13 x 4 mm (20 plies) were tested at L/d of 60 as recommended by Zweben et al. (14). Specimens were tested at a speed of 20 mm/min. ECPE modulus specimens with nominal dimensions 300 x 10 x 4 mm (12 plies) were tested using a support span of 240 mm at a speed of 5 mm/min. The flexural modulus, E_B, was calculated from:

$$E_B = k_1 \frac{L^3 m}{4bd^3} \quad (3)$$

where L is the length of the support span, m is the slope of the initial linear portion of the load-deflection curve, b is the specimen width, d is the specimen thickness and k₁ is 0.25 for the three-point method (aramid) and 0.21 for the four-point method (ECPE).

The flexural strength of the aramid/epoxy composites was determined using specimens of nominal dimensions 150 x 13 x 4 mm and L/d of 32, at a speed of 5 mm/min. For ECPE, flexural strength specimens of nominal dimension 80 x 10 x 4 mm were tested using a support span of 64 mm and a load span of 21.3 mm at a speed of 5 mm/min. The flexural strength, S , is given by:

$$S = k_2 \frac{PL}{bd^2} \quad (4)$$

where L is the length of the support span, P , b and d are defined as above and k_2 is 1.5 for the three-point method and 1 for the four-point method.

2.7 Fracture Surface Examination The fracture surfaces were coated with gold, and were examined in a Cambridge S250 Stereo-scan Mark 2 scanning electron microscope (SEM) using secondary electrons.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Plasma Surface Amination Fabrics were plasma treated in ammonia for times ranging from 0.25 to 20 min. The fibre surface amine concentration was determined as a function of time using the technique described above. The results are plotted in Figure 1. For aramid fabrics, the surface amine concentration reaches a limiting value of about 0.4 groups per nm^2 after a treatment time of 30 s. For ECPE fabrics, however, the concentration continues to increase with time. This difference is probably due to the greater number of sites on ECPE to which an amine can be grafted.

FIGURE 1. Fibre surface amine concentration as a function of ammonia plasma treatment time for (\square) aramid (\circ) ECPE.

3.2 Interlaminar Shear Strength The ILSS of composites made with untreated and plasma-treated fabrics and corona treated ECPE fabric were calculated using Equation 2 and are presented in Table 1. The significant

TABLE 1 DEGREE OF SURFACE AMINATION, MATRIX CONTENT AND INTERLAMINAR SHEAR STRENGTH OF ARAMID/EPOXY AND ECPE/EPOXY COMPOSITES

Material and Surface Treatment	Amine groups per nm ²	Matrix Content (weight %)	Interlaminar Shear Strength (MPa)
Aramid - none	-	33.6	24.2 ± 0.4
Aramid - 30 s ammonia plasma	0.4	32.8	30.9 ± 0.5
Aramid - 5 min ammonia plasma	0.56	32.6	33.2 ± 1.2
ECPE - none	-	34.6	5.7 ± 0.3
ECPE - 1 min ammonia plasma	0.49	37.9	11.1 ± 0.3
ECPE - 10 min ammonia plasma	1.75	35.4	11.8 ± 1.9
ECPE - Corona discharge	-	35.2	7.0 ± 0.8

improvements in ILSS for both aramids and ECPE when the fabrics are treated in an ammonia plasma prior to composite fabrication are due to an increase in fibre/matrix interface strength. This is evidenced by fracture surface micrographs (Figures 2 and 3). For composites made from untreated fabrics, failure has occurred at the fibre/matrix interface (Figure 2). For composites made from treated fabrics, this is no longer the dominant failure mode and the aramid composites exhibit fibre fibrillation and matrix cracking while the ECPE composites experience additional shear failure within the fibres (Figure 3). It appears that for the latter the fibre/matrix interface strength increases until it exceeds the shear strength of the fibres. This explains the change in failure mode and the lack of further improvement in ILSS at prolonged treatment times. These results are consistent with increased fibre/matrix adhesion due to chemical bonding between the amine groups on the fibre surface and the epoxy resin, although direct evidence is difficult to obtain. The aramid/epoxy ILSS results are in general accord with those of Stoller and Allred (15), who observed similar effects in T-peel experiments on 2-ply laminates. The increase in ECPE/epoxy ILSS after treatment in a corona discharge is less than that obtained by plasma treatment, and probably arises from the increased wettability associated with oxygen-containing functional groups on the fibre surface. Similar results have been obtained by Kaplan et al. (9) for woven ECPE/epoxy composites containing untreated, corona treated and oxygen-containing-gas plasma-treated fibres, although Ladizesky and Ward (8) have reported significantly larger ILSS for composites made from untreated and oxygen plasma-treated melt-spun polyethylene.

3.3 Flexural Properties Flexural properties were calculated using Equations 3 and 4 and are presented in Table 2. Figure 4 shows typical load versus deflection curves for aramid and ECPE composites containing untreated

FIGURE 2. Interlaminar shear fracture surfaces of composites made from untreated fibres showing clean fibre/matrix separation: (a) Aramid/epoxy; (b) ECPE/epoxy.

fibres and ammonia plasma-treated fibres. It is evident from Figure 4 and Table 2 that plasma treatment of the fibres has no significant effect on the flexural modulus of aramid/epoxy composites. This result confirms the general expectation that the flexural modulus is determined primarily by the tensile and compressive properties of the fibre and matrix, rather than by interfacial properties. The load-deflection behaviour of all aramid/epoxy specimens becomes non-linear above loads of 150 Newtons, but those made from untreated and treated fibres behave quite differently. The former start to fail at relatively low deflections, although they do not fail catastrophically until much higher deflections. However, for composites made from plasma-treated

FIGURE 3. Interlaminar shear fracture surfaces of composites made from ammonia plasma-treated fibres showing (a) aramid fibre fibrillation and matrix cracking, and (b) internal shearing of ECPE fibres.

fibres, the load continues to increase until catastrophic failure takes place. The flexural strengths of the aramid/epoxy composite specimens presented in Table 2 show an increase of ~38% after 30 s plasma treatment of the fibres and ~45% after 5 min treatment. In general, the mechanism of flexural failure is a complex process in which tensile, compressive and shear failure modes may be induced to varying degrees in each of the composite phases. Non-linearity in flexural load-deflection behaviour of aramid composites has been observed by Zweben (14,16) and Allred (17), and is attributed to compressive failure in the flexural test specimens. It has been shown that the compressive

TABLE 2 MATRIX CONTENT AND FLEXURAL PROPERTIES OF
ARAMID/EPOXY AND ECPE/EPOXY COMPOSITES

Material and Surface Treatment	Matrix Content (weight %)	Flexural Modulus (GPa)	Flexural Strength (MPa)
Aramid - none	33.6	31.0 ± 0.7	305 ± 16
Aramid - 30 s ammonia plasma	32.8	32.5 ± 1.1	421 ± 18
Aramid - 5 min ammonia plasma	32.6	32.5 ± 0.8	442 ± 18
ECPE - none	35.0	1.34 ± 0.14	33.4 ± 0.6
ECPE - 1 min ammonia plasma	35.0	5.06 ± 0.17	62.9 ± 2.7
ECPE - 10 min ammonia plasma	35.5	5.04 ± 0.22	67.7 ± 3.4
ECPE - Corona discharge	32.4	4.60 ± 0.31	51.7 ± 1.5

FIGURE 4. Plot of composite flexural load as a function of beam deflection for aramid/epoxy made from (a) untreated fibres and (b) ammonia plasma-treated fibres, and ECPE/epoxy made from (c) untreated fibres and (d) ammonia plasma-treated fibres.

stress-strain curves of unidirectional aramid/epoxy composites are strongly non-linear (16), and that the compressive strength is only about 20% of the tensile strength (18,19). The latter has been attributed to a buckling or kinking failure in the aramid fibres (18) or to a combination of low fibre compressive strength and a low fibre/matrix interfacial strength (19).

Microscopic examination of the failure modes in flexural test specimens made from untreated and plasma-treated aramid fibres shows that the former contain

more extensive fibre buckling and debonding which extend further into the composite from the compression surface. Both sets of specimens also fail on the tensile surface at maximum strain, and microscopic examination shows matrix cracking and fibre/matrix debonding along fibres transverse to the tensile stress direction. These results indicate that the enhanced flexural strength of aramid/epoxy composites after fibre plasma treatment is due mainly to a decrease in compressive fibre debonding, which is due in turn to increased fibre/matrix interfacial bonding.

The flexural modulus and strength values for ECPE/epoxy composites, presented in Table 2, show that plasma surface treatment increases the flexural modulus by ~250% and the flexural strength by ~100%. These results, particularly the increase in flexural modulus, are different from those obtained for aramid/epoxy composites, and may be attributed to the very low surface energy of untreated ECPE fibres. Similar increases in flexural modulus and strength of ECPE/epoxy composites after fibre surface treatment have been reported by other authors (10,13). In particular, Kaplan et al. (10) found that the increase in flexural modulus after surface treatment was greater for composites made from woven fabrics than for unidirectional composites, and that an oxygen-containing-gas plasma treatment gave a significantly higher flexural modulus than did corona treatment.

In ECPE/epoxy composites made from untreated fibres, no catastrophic flexural failure was observed, and the flexural strength results presented in Table 2 were obtained using loads corresponding to a maximum fibre strain of 5% (Equation 4). A typical trace is shown in Figure 4c. Composites made from surface-treated fibres all exhibited maximum loads at a fibre strain of about 5% (Figure 4d). All flexural specimens showed compressive failure but no obvious tensile failure was observed. The improvement after fibre treatment is again attributed to a decrease in compressive fibre buckling and debonding resulting from a stronger fibre/matrix interfacial bond, which in this case is also sufficient to result in a substantial increase in flexural modulus.

4. CONCLUSIONS

Ammonia plasma treatment of aramid and ECPE fibre surfaces results in substantial increases in shear strength and flexural strength of aramid/epoxy and ECPE/epoxy composites. For ECPE/epoxy composites a marked increase in flexural modulus is also observed. These changes are related to the introduction of surface amine groups which enhance the bonding between the fibres and the epoxy matrix, resulting in changes in the interlaminar failure mechanisms. The interlaminar shear results are in accord with scanning electron microscopic examinations of fracture surfaces which show clean fibre/matrix separation in the untreated fibre composites and additional evidence of fibre and matrix failure in composites containing treated fibres. Optical microscopic examinations show that the increased flexural properties

of treated fibre composites can be attributed to a lower degree of compressive fibre buckling due to enhanced interfacial bonding. The flexural modulus results demonstrate that the fibre/matrix interface properties contribute more significantly to the flexural modulus of ECPE/epoxy composites than to that of aramid/epoxy composites.

5. REFERENCES

1. M. Breznick, J. Banjabi, H. Guttman and G. Marom, Polym. Commun., **28**, 55 (1987).
2. T. S. Keller, A. S. Hoffman, B. D. Ratner and B. J. McElroy in K. L. Mittal, ed., Physicochemical Aspects of Polymer Surfaces, Vol. 2, Plenum Press, New York, 1983, pp. 861 - 879.
3. Y. Wu and G. C. Tesoro, J. Appl. Polym. Sci., **31**, 1041 (1986).
4. L. S. Penn, T. J. Byerley and T. K. Liao, J. Adhesion, **23**, 163 (1987).
5. L. S. Penn, G. C. Tesoro and H. X. Zhou, Polym. Compos., **9**, 184 (1988).
6. R. E. Allred, "Surface Chemical Modification of Polyaramid Filaments with Amine Plasmas", Ph.D. Thesis, Massachusetts Institute of Technology, 1983, pp. 39, 130, 131.
7. G. A. George and H. A. Willis, High Perf. Polym., **1**, 335 (1990).
8. N. H. Ladizesky and I. M. Ward, Compos. Sci. Technol., **26**, 129 (1986).
9. S. L. Kaplan, P. W. Rose, H. X. Nguyen and H. W. Chang, SAMPE International Symposium, **33**, 551 (1988).
10. H. X. Nguyen, G. C. Weedon and H. W. Chang, SAMPE International Symposium, **34**, 1603 (1989).
11. C. E. Browning, F. L. Abrams and J. M. Whitney, ASTM STP, **797**, 54 (1983).
12. "Apparent Interlaminar Shear Strength of Parallel Fiber Composites by Short-Beam Method", ASTM D2344-76 (1976).
13. "Standard Test Methods for Flexural Properties of Unreinforced and Reinforced Plastics and Electrical Insulating Materials", ASTM D790-86 (1986).
14. C. Zweben, W. S. Smith and M. W. Wardle, ASTM STP, **674**, 228 (1978).
15. H. M. Stoller and R. E. Allred, SAMPE International Technical Conference, **18**, 993 (1986).
16. C. Zweben, J. Compos. Mater., **12**, 422 (1978).
17. R. E. Allred, J. Compos. Mater., **15**, 100, 117 (1981).
18. J. H. Greenwood and P. G. Rose, J. Mater. Sci., **9**, 1809 (1974).
19. S. V. Kulkarni, J. S. Rice and B. W. Rosen, Composites, **6**, 217 (1975).

BIOGRAPHIES

Dr James Brown is a principal research scientist in the Protective Chemistry Division of the Materials Research Laboratory. He graduated in physical chemistry BSc (Hons) from the University of Queensland in 1966, and was awarded a PhD in 1970 from the same University for research into high-energy radiation effects on polysulfone polymers. In the same year he joined the Materials Research Laboratory where he has been involved in a number of organic material technology areas such as thermal properties and fire hazards, high performance fibres, high energy laser effects, chemical survivability, lightweight ballistic protection and properties of advanced fibre reinforced organic matrix composites.

Dr Philip Chappell is a senior research scientist in the Protective Chemistry Division of the Materials Research Laboratory. He graduated in physical chemistry BSc (Hons) from the Australian National University in 1976, and was awarded a PhD in 1981 from the University of California, Los Angeles for research into light scattering from molecular liquids. After post-doctoral work on XPS of tungsten oxide catalysts at the Flinders University of South Australia, he joined the Materials Research Laboratory in 1983. He has since been involved in work on surface modification and characterisation of advanced organic fibres, and the properties of advanced fibre reinforced organic matrix composites.

Zdenka Mathys is an experimental scientist in the Protective Chemistry Division of the Materials Research Laboratory. She graduated in applied chemistry from Footscray Institute of Technology in 1985. Since joining Materials Research Laboratory in 1986 she has been involved in work on surface modification and characterisation of aramid and polyethylene fibres, and the mechanical, physical and impact properties of organic matrix composites.

